

THE POWER OF THE SCREEN - ANGEL or DEVIL

The damage to human life from TVs, computers and phones.

By Dr. Alan Wenham-Prosser D.Prof., MA.

This paper looks at the evolution of the screen on which we now look at the internet and at our friends on the smart-phone. I am an octogenarian, and this means I can remember life without any screens in the home. I have observed the evolution of the screen in the home from television, to computer then internet and finally the smart-phone. Few people living today can know how the screen has taken control of human thinking and therefore most aspects of human life. To be able to really measure the scale of this control a person needs to have good memory of life without any screen. Most people younger than 70 or 75 will not have the experience or the knowledge to compare modern life against life with no screen in the home. It is essential to have a proper view of this.

Very few have escaped the control which the screen now has; or the power it has over our thinking. This includes doctors, academics, scientists and politicians.; all the people who have important control of our lives. This paper is for all people an essential guide towards enacting controls which have now become more necessary than at any time in human history. Most politicians are so controlled by screens in their lives that this weakens them from being able to protect children under 18 years from the many dangers which the screen now poses. It is because most of them know no life without the power of the screen that they are both blind and paralysed to making essential controls.

Although I have to admit that the use of my laptop and screen, in conjunction with the internet has facilitated the production and distribution of this document, and many others of mine. Hence my use of the screen is for the education and benefit of others. However, readers should know that both my wife and I, since before 1971 have not had a television in our home (now 54 years). Neither will we ever have a smart phone. Hence there is no obsessive addiction to the screen for us in the way many people do have. Believe me, it is a happier life and a life of lower stress to have no smart phone and no television. You can live without these things. Human society lived without them for many millennia.

Our three children all excelled above their peers at school due to having the ability to pay attention far greater than any other students during lesson times. All the teachers noticed this and asked us to explain how it was possible. The "no television" was the answer which they agreed was the reason for the children's success at school. Most children's attention span is now measured in seconds rather than minutes. A factor of sixty.

From the position of not being in any way addicted to a screen, it is possible I am one of the very few academic people who can comment objectively about the adverse nature of its power. I actually wish I could live a life with no need for a screen at all.

Read on and enjoy.

CONTENTS

Introduction	2	The Power of Advertising on TV	5
The Advent of Television	2	The Power of the Computer Screen	6
The Power of the Screen Illusion.	3	The Smart-phone Screen	8
The Power of False Authority	4	Damage to Life From Online Possibilities	9

Introduction

Prior to the screens coming into our houses we only had cinema in one form or another. This was merely an entertainment which only gave people either information or enjoyment. In the beginning there was no intention or use of cinema to supplant the general thinking of the ordinary person. Later this changed and cinema became a propaganda machine; or a method to influence people's opinions. But by that time screens had already begun to appear in people's homes in the form of television.

If we are honest, the screen today has become the means to commit crimes of every kind onto persons who are remote from the criminal. Never before in history, has a person of another culture with a different language and many thousands of miles from the victim, been able to commit crime on them by the use of a remotely controlled screen. What is astonishing is the fact that many people nowadays will believe more of what a screen tells them than a real person standing in front of them with better advice.

Across the world and throughout history whole nations have risen to fight off invaders or dictators who have sought to take control of their lives. Yet in this 21st century billions of, so called, intelligent people have allowed the smart phone to take over their lives without any resistance. The smart phone is now the biggest cause of the 1.5 million traffic accidents in the UK. In 2024 more than 3,000 people lost their lives in the USA due to the use of telephones while driving vehicles. Surely this is a cause for our serious concern.

Smart phone fraud is the largest loss of money to ordinary people in the UK where more than UK£1 billion is stolen every year. These facts make the losses by tyrants and invaders look small. The smart phone is the 21st century successful invader; it is a devil.

Politicians have not really awoken to this power because they are asleep to its existence. They are also victims of it and users of its power. Hence they have mental blindness to its existence. For this reason it is the ordinary person that has to make some attempt to turn the clock back to the day when we all could think for ourselves, without the control of the screen taking over our mental processes of decision and comprehension.

The Advent of Television

When I was a child in the 1940s there was cinema but no television. There was no national broadcast television in those years. It started in the 1950s when I was about 6 or 7 years old. I remember this because my father was trained by the UK Government to be a television engineer. He had suffered disabilities from the second-world-war as a soldier, who played a vital role in that war, using powerful artillery which fired across the North Sea horizon at targets worked out by other intelligence methods. As compensation and a means to get him into employment he was given the latest technological training in the new phenomenon of television (TV). Eventually, many years later, he became so good at it, that he was able to construct his own colour TV from scratch with all the components that he needed. He was a genius with television construction and repair.

In the beginning he rented a small shop round the corner to our street in SE London, where he repaired the TV's of the richer people in our area who had one in their home. Normal people had no spare money to afford such a luxury; they were very expensive in those days. Hence we often had one of these in our house for testing purposes after the repairs had been done. We were the first family in our street to have a TV in the home; albeit a short term borrow for testing purposes. All our childhood friends would come in and watch this new machine in the home. This was when I was about 8 or 9 years old. (early 1950s). I saw then the mesmerising and magical effect it had on my friends.

These childhood friends would normally be making noise and being very active. Most things we did together involved a lot of talking and physical movement. Then I saw in my home the sudden change in them all. Sitting in front of the TV; no one spoke and no one moved. Until that time no other thing in the home had the power to stop a group of children from moving and talking. This was the beginning of the effect of the screen on the health of the nation. Slowly the nation would become less active and more sedentary; leading to the ill effects of reduced physical exercise. But no one knew about this phenomenon of less exercise in those days; because it had never been something which affected large numbers of people. Hence the gradual creep of the effect of the screen was not being checked or being observed.

Such is the nature of all modern technology. It brings with it problems which have not been in society previously; hence no one notices it until it is too late; viz the internet – the greatest angel/evil man has ever known. Those in charge are generally unaware of this.

This is another subject of how blind European type people are to the consequences of new inventions which they deem “progress” when the end result is harm to life on this planet. Such things as CFC gases, plastics, nuclear power and the motor car are only a few. I am sure my readers can think of few others. It was Europeans who invented these.

Some of the so called “clever” European inventions have not proved to be clever mainly because the inventors did not carry out a full risk assessment of the possible effects of their invention or the possible uses which criminals could make with it. This is the modern “Pandora’s Box”. A full risk assessment of the internet would have controlled its public use. Full and verified identification should be the first thing before allowing any person access to the internet. I need such a thing to drive a car; the internet has proved to be far more dangerous than a car. Many people lose their lives due to the internet.

Back to the TV subject. Many people will not know; but there was in the 1950s in the UK only the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) which had Government permission to broadcast TV programs; one TV channel.

Note:- the BBC is not a UK Government organisation, it is a stand-alone independent organisation. Also the first broadcasts were only from an early time in the evening until about 11.00 p.m. Then the BBC broadcast would shut down with the National Anthem; probably about six hours or less of TV programs. So the combination of one channel and a few hours would not then affect the health of the nation to a great extent.

The Power of the Screen Illusion

Let’s examine how scenes on a flat screen are a multiple illusion. Firstly we should know that the apparent movement we see of people and objects on a screen is not real movement. The first cinema screen movies were a clear example of this. The images were seen to be a quick succession of still pictures, each one a little different to the previous picture. Due to the ability of the human eye to very briefly retain a previous image, the next image blends with the previous image to give the false impression that we are seeing a moving scene; when in reality we are seeing a series of still pictures quickly presented to the eyes. This means the movement we think we see is not the real time movement we see in real life. Hence screen movement is an illusion. Modern cinema films have improved away from the early methods and now have a very quick succession of still pictures. All now transferred into digital images.

The cinema idea was repeated with television cameras. Here it was not a series of actual pictures like the early cinema films, it is a very fast electrical scan made, but very quick still pictures blended in rapid sequence. Again giving the illusion that we are seeing live movement. The same thing happens now with so called videos with smart phones or

laptop computers. What the software program does is to take 30 or more still pictures every second and show them very quickly to the human sense of sight. Again this creates the illusion of real movement; which is really only many still pictures.

Next, the scenes from all the above ways of presenting images appear to be three dimensional; in the same way we see the world with our eyes. But we all know, when we think about it, that none of these scenes have any real depth. The cinema screen is flat; it has no real depth to it. The same is true of television screens, smart-phone and computer screens. They are fractions of one millimetre in depth. We are never seeing real three dimensions in any of these screen presentations. It is an illusion of three dimensions.

Next subject; colours. The same illusion is true of the colours we see on screens. All these methods of producing images use the, so called, three prime colours along with black and no colour (white). The clever manipulation and mixing of these has provided a vast array of available colours to appear before our eyes; they are made from very small colour cells of the few colours mentioned above, so as to give the illusion of other colours. But none of them are as nature provides. They are all approximations. Hence it is another illusion of the screen.

With both many of the television and cinema pictures we believe we are looking in onto scene from the lives of the actors and participants. What we do not see is the vast array of cameras, microphones, lighting and technicians who are behind the camera controlling the final scene which we see. Also the final story as presented is a collage of many separate scenes recorded at different times, maybe over many days and weeks. It is not happening in a continuous stream which we believe is happening. With such things as television the final presentation may be an edited version of many parts, put together to seem like a continuous scene.

Here we have clearly an illusion created by clever technology to seem like real life situations or the record of real happenings. Yet in all those ways above it is clearly a clever illusion which carries with it the convincing power of those who have created it.

In modern times we can now add the dimension of what is called "artificial intelligence" (AI) which is not really intelligent at all. But has the ability to create and combine pictures and sounds which have never existed in the material world. But because the illusion of the screen has become established in the lives of most people, the AI is able to ride upon that legacy and convince the human mind that what is showing is from real life.

The Power of False Authority

There was another strong effect that TV was having on the mind of the nation. This was the false authority which people attributed to the facts and information which TV program put into the minds of people. If a subject was examined or reported on a TV documentary or the news program, it carried an authority which seemed to overpower normal common sense. But we all know that journalists and news people see an event from a particular viewpoint. This was the hidden element which the population did not notice. They were getting a biased view; albeit the BBC were not aware of this; and had a policy of no bias in their reporting. But for a person to be free of opinions is very hard.

Many years later, whilst waiting to act as prosecutor & witness to one of my Building Control cases in the court waiting room; I got into a conversation with a police officer who was also waiting for his case to be called. We talked about the difficulty of witnesses and getting a case proved. He told me that if there had been a serious accident with several witnesses, that when he began to compare all the witness statements, they were all as if each person had seen a different accident. He said that in amongst all the statements the true story was there. But not one of them had really witnessed or remembered the whole

event accurately. Such is the weakness of human observation. **We must not forget this.** Yet each person would have been willing to stand in a court of law and swear the truth.

Hence it is difficult to believe that we really get either the true story or the whole story from journalists or news reporters. The same can be true of scientists and medical reports. See my paper "Human Mental Blindness" [<https://www.academia.edu/45180280>] for a full exposition of this subject. It is very important to fully embrace this phenomenon.

So when people were telling their facts on TV in the 1950s, people would falsely assume the facts were 100% true. I often heard the comment from people, "**But I saw it on TV so it must be true.**" This was a very common psychology of the effect of information broadcast on TV. No one knows how it was that TV gained, as if the power of God Himself, as being 100% true and believable. But this was the effect of the new phenomenon which the TV screen had introduced into the life of the nation. It continues now through the internet, social media and smart-phones. Few people notice this power which it has.

It could hardly happen these days, but in the late 1950's there were often conversations between a person who had no TV at home and one who was reporting on (so called) facts s/he had seen on TV. The non-TV owner would be refuting the facts based on common sense. The TV owner would be empowered by the false authority of the TV screen. There would be little meeting ground in their dispute. This was another effect of the screen on the life of the nation; as well as the potential for less exercise. In many ways we have become a nation abandoning common sense and true facts for the power of the screen.

In those days the morning and daytime would be a busy time for most people. Children going to school; dads going to work and the majority of mums doing housework and shopping etc. Few people would have time to sit **doing nothing** other than staring at a box in the corner of the room. Hence the health effect on lack of exercise was not a sudden thing. Slowly the program times would increase. Children's television would be broadcast after school time in the afternoon. And eventually to satisfy shift and night workers, TV programs were on most of the day. But one good thing about BBC television was that it received its funding through the TV licence from the year 1946. Hence there was no need for obtaining funds from advertising. The advent of the first commercial TV program, was when I was about 11 years old. Then we began to see advertising for products on the television; but only on the independent TV programs. This brought in a new and serious effect on the minds of people. This was the origin of consumerism.

The Power of Advertising on the TV Screens

With the advent of TV advertising the nation began to find out about new products; also reminded about the standard products which most people used and knew. The advertising industry had received a huge boost and started to become a powerful force. It is now the richest force on the internet through the power of the simple click. The time around the 1950s and 1960s was called the golden age of advertising. TV advertising became very clever. Catchy tunes and humorous cartoons attracted people's minds and they found themselves buying items in the shops which they may not really have needed. The beginnings of consumerism. The price increase to cover advertising costs can be as much as 5%. But many would say that advertising brings prices down due to increased competition and economies of scale. Mass media advertising is very costly. Product profits must pay for it.

The advertising companies were quick to notice the power which the screen had on people's minds; the false authority mentioned above. In the 1950s very nasty form of advertising was developed which used a sort of subliminal form of getting people to buy items. Hidden within the TV advert was a quick flash of a message which the normal con-

scious mind did not notice. This message could be impressed on the person's thinking. The aim was to boost sales of a product. Some people found themselves buying things they did not need. When it was out in the open this practise was frowned upon.

Yet most people would say that they are not affected by advertising. The sales departments of major companies would not agree. There was no agreement 60 years ago as to whether subliminal advertising worked or not. Hence, it stopped in its covert form and instead reappeared in the form of catchy logos or trademarks. There is no doubt that advertising works; but has it resulted in consumerism? The dreaded phenomenon of people buying things they either do not need, or they rarely, if ever use. Rubbish dumps (now called recycling centres) are overloaded with products which have not been fully used; and people no longer need. Most houses are cluttered with items that get little use or are not really needed. Thousands of tons of such material is discarded every day in the UK. The effect on the environment is devastating. Much of this is due to the power of the screen when used for advertising. Another European invention with bad end results.

The Power of the Computer + Screen

My first encounter with computer programming was in 1966 when studying for Civil Engineering at Kingston-upon-Thames west of London. A primitive machine the size of a small bedroom included a paper tape producing typewriter and a large computing machine that stood 1.75 m from the floor. A thousand times the power of that machine is now held in people's hands as a telephone/camera/ video recorder/computer etc.

The first computers could be constructed by anyone with electrician's knowledge. He would use valves, resistors, capacitors, inductors, transformers and normal wires to connect all these things. The tasks of these things have now been taken over by the tiny micro-chips; such as are inside the hand held mega-computer called the smart-phone.

We young budding engineers spent a hour or more, on the large machine described above, calculating engineering problems which we could do '**normally**' in five minutes without a computer. Now very few engineers know how to do these things the '**normal**' way. This means that if they did not have some form of computing device they would be unable to perform their function as an engineer. This is the seriously damaging effect of the computer + screen (and calculator). The same applies to architects and many other professionals. Humanity has lost contact with manual ways of doing almost every complex task. This includes many normal office tasks once done with pen and paper. The modern world has become the prisoner of the computer micro-chip and computer software. As with all things, computers will have an ending one day. Nothing on this planet lasts forever. If this demise of the microchip and / or computer is sudden, mankind will fall suddenly into a dark age of ignorance about many things which have taken centuries to build up; simply because those people who knew how to do things manually may not be around to help. Future historians will wonder how stupid mankind can become.

Therefore the modern world has become dependent on those places where micro-chips (called semi-conductors) can be produced. This means that the running and organising of about 190 countries depends on the production of microchips from about seven areas of the world. Of those countries which have the knowledge and capacity to produce micro-chips 70% of the production of them is from only three countries; China, Taiwan and South Korea. All three of these countries are not stable governments and do not have very stable economies either; compared to the western type countries with established democracies. Is the human world at risk by allowing its control to be in the hands of so few? As we have seen in 2025 with the USA and Russia, global trade and co-operation can

come to a sudden crisis. Then the vital parts for the technology may be difficult to procure.

Many millions of semi-conductors are required every year; and are now vital to the production of most complex items. Without these micro-chips the world cannot function.

The main areas of human life today are (1) electricity production, (2) food, includes farming, (3) travel (train, ship and air); includes trade transport, (4) communication, (5) health services, (6) banking and (7) manufacturing processes. All seven of these, and many others, are vital to the running of any country. All of these have now become completely controlled by the micro-chip. Never before in the history of the human race has its survival become dependent on a single tiny complex item. An item which has such complexity that it requires other micro-chips to ensure that it is tested and working properly; and very few people know how to design them, test them and make them work properly. Also governments or programmers can ensure that secretive routines are embedded into these microchips. These can then be used to disrupt processes or to spy on people and countries remotely. Another European invention with harmful outcomes.

The computer programme is a complex control system. Very few people know what goes on inside computer programmes; or where the program may be connecting to parts of the world remote from where it is working. This is due the other thing called the internet. (more about that later). But as a taste of what this means, the UK postal company called The Royal Mail, used a computer programme to run the accounts system to connect the many thousands of Post Offices across the UK. The computer program "apparently" malfunctioned and many UK £millions disappeared from the system. The post office staff were incorrectly accused and prosecuted for stealing the money. Many lives were ruined; many were incorrectly put into prison. It has finally been accepted that the computer programme was at fault; **or was it at fault?** The whereabouts of the lost money has not been discovered or even investigated. It is not beyond the capability of a computer programmer to put a hidden sub-routine into the accounts software with all necessary bank transfer information in it. Then at random intervals to send money from random post offices' accounts to the secret bank account of the computer programmer; done in a few seconds. There is not one person in the Royal Mail who has the capacity to know what is really going on inside that computer programme. The connection to the internet is the main function of that programme so as to run the UK Post Office accounts system. Who knows what the programme was doing when it connected with the internet? The money must be somewhere. No one has asked this publicly before. It is how the bugs known as "Trojans" work. Hidden and working without anyone knowing. To spy on people through such software would be as easy as that.

So what do we have with the computer + screen? A machine which controls what we do, but we have no knowledge of how it works or all the things it is actually doing. And no knowledge or ability to fix it, if it malfunctions. The above is only one example of the danger to human life by depending on the power of the screen. Many wiser governments are refusing to allow computing facilities manufactured in the Far Eastern countries listed above; because of the fear that information may be covertly sent to those countries through the devices which they have made. What does this tell us? That many governments have no way of knowing what goes on inside machines which are controlled by semiconductors and computer programmes, and of necessity are connected to the internet; hence their only remedy is to resort to not using them.

This same power is now used by criminals to subjugate (hack) the computers and their software in the running of businesses, electricity distribution networks, government

operations and many other vital services which many communities could not function well without; people looking at screens 1,000s of miles away where they cannot be caught or prosecuted, causing the lives of thousands (or millions) of people to be adversely affected. How ignorant these people who originate from Europe have been over this issue.

How the power of the screen, from its harmless initial use, has now become the factor which determines whether or not so many things function. The real question is; **“How did mankind allow himself to be in such a vulnerable situation of the power of the screen over his entire life?”** When such screens are no longer in use (which must happen one day), how will those future historians describe the ignorance and stupidity of our current age? Mankind has shown that he cannot learn from lessons of the past.

The Smart-phone Screen

The above development of the power of the screen is now walking about most streets in developed communities or places where smart-phones are the normal thing to have. As mentioned earlier; my wife and I understood and would not accept the power of the screen to control our thinking since before we were married in 1971. My observation of the power of the screen started in the 1950's before I was a teenager; $\frac{3}{4}$ of a century ago. Hence we are part of the tiny minority of people who will not accept either a television or a smart-phone into the workings of our psychology. Few people realise how this liberates their life to choose what to do and how to live each day. It needs the human mind and intellect to be fully awake to see this power; which the screen has over the behaviour and the thinking of the person. The mind and intellect of most people is asleep; although walking around the streets as if they are in control of their lives. Sleep walking.

In 2004, prior to the computer type smart-phone era, the average attention span on a screen for adults was 90 seconds. Less than twenty years later it was one quarter of this. The change has been attributed to the multi-ap smart-phone.

Criminals across the world have learned very quickly how to use this power of the screen and the connection of the microchip to the internet. They are constantly working on how to control people's lives and steal their wealth. Their main target is now the smart-phone user. One of the many original claims for the use of computers and screens is that the functions they carry out make life less expensive. The predicted cost of cyber crime in the UK for 2025 is £524 billion. This equals approximately £8,000 for every single person in the UK; or £19,000 per average household. This is about 50% of the average family annual income. How can we say that computers and screens have made life cheaper? Life is certainly better without the screen and the computer, less expensive and far less stressful. But few people have the courage to live like that. Human weakness.

The mesmerising power which the screen has and the false authority which it conveys is the power which started with the television advertising 75 years ago; it is now very established. The modern generation do not know life without the intervention of screens. Hence billions of people across the world are now holding a serious weapon in their hands; and very few people are able to resist using it or resist the power which it has. Neither are they aware of its power over their lives; since themselves and their parents have become mentally prisoners of the screen and they think this is normal life. It is not normal life. Normal life is that to which we would all resort to without all the modern aids which the technological revolution has created; and which have been slipped into our lives without sufficient risk assessment of their effect. In terms of the screen, my wife and myself live almost a normal life. My wife does not use the internet at all.

There is now a mental disorder recognised by many health professionals in the UK called "Nomophobia" =[**NO MO**bile-phone **PHOBIA**.] It is the irrational fear of being without the mobile phone. Sickness caused by screens. It has recognised symptoms :-

1. Intense anxiety about not having the mobile phone during the day.
2. Stress about the remaining electrical charge in the battery.
3. Irrational fear of missing vital news or information.
4. Panic when /if there is no Wi-Fi or another phone connection.
5. Difficulty concentrating on important issues at hand. (i.e. driving a vehicle)

The main reason for this fear has been self-imposed by those who suffer from it. Because each person has decided to give various functions of their life to the phone. Such functions have a long list:-

- A. Continuous connection with friends or family.
- B. Paying for travel on bus, metro or train.
- C. Paying for things as small as a cup of coffee.
- D. Not carrying cash when the phone may be offline or malfunctions.
- E. Directions of how to get to places.

Many schools in the UK put strong restrictions on children bringing smart-phones into the school. Yet the same schools require those children to use screens in the classroom (tablet computers) or to go home and research on the internet matters connected with homework, more screen time. So their policy of restriction is undermined by their own policy to rely on screens for educational purposes. Recently the people of Australia have recognised the power of the screen on the lives of children. They are in the process of restricting children from accessing social media. Which is known to be the cause of much anxiety and even suicides in the teenage population. If children find out that they can live happily without social media, maybe they will have a chance to become free from the power of the screen in their lives.

Statistics say that the modern generation of UK children have eyesight badly affected by too much close focus onto screens. Also many children are not walking upright. When on public streets they are 80% of the time with head bent forward onto a screen. This will become a permanent characteristic of their posture in time.

Damage to Human Life From Online Possibilities

Social media is not only a problem for under 18 year olds. Many people can manage it in their lives. But many are addicted to it and really believe it is necessary in their lives. But they have not seen that their life has been constructed around the advent of social media. Simply because they have hardly known life without it. They cannot see the damage it does to their psychology. It is all accepted as normal life. Because unlike people such as myself and my wife, they have not known the happiness which life can have every day without it.

It is the screen which has brought such harmful things as pornography. Not only harmful to those who view it, but harmful to those people coerced or trapped into providing it. Many innocent young ladies, attracted by large offers of cash, have had their lives ruined by it. Altogether society would be a better place without it. We cannot know how many men have committed sex crimes due to the effects of seeing what they should not have seen. Or without the screen would never have had the chance to see. It is estimated that globally (2024) that 300 million children have become victims of sex crimes due to the effect of online pornographic behaviour.

We can add to the above the use of on-line gambling. Many millions of people's lives have been financially ruined due to the ease by which they are able to click money into the bank accounts of others, in the mistaken belief that they will eventually become rich with cash. This number is estimated to be around 450 million adults worldwide in 2024. Such problem gambling accounts for the greater part of the income of those who work out the computer programs. It is really intentional theft. Only those who know how to make it attractive and also know how to balance the odds in their own favour, are the ones who become rich. Intelligent and moral governments would make it illegal. The excuse that people will only find unregulated sites if it was illegal is not responsible government or tenable to the rational person. The same can be said about many illegal things.

There is no doubt that the screen has provided many good opportunities for many people. This I am sure is a strong argument in favour of the screen. But are we able to ask the question, "Can we not provide all that the screen does without it?"

This phenomena of the screen is very recent in terms of human history. A recent discovery in the UK put the existence of intelligent human life at 400,000 years ago. If this time span were equated to one day of 24 hours, then the screen has only been with us for less than 25 seconds since those early humans. We have a long way to go. And it is certain that digital technology will not last for even one more minute in that day of human existence. How will human society continue when the digital age has ended?

Here lies the power of the screen - to put human society at risk of continuation.